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Annotation: the article carried out a comprehensive diagnostics of the infrastructure railway transport, diagnostics subgrade, diagnostics subgrade using the Geoscanner, as well as high-speed diagnostic complex for automated assessment of the state of technical infrastructure facilities related to traffic safety trains

Key words: subgrade diagnostics, monitoring, defect, GEOSCANNER, GPR,

Introduction: The work is devoted to solving the problem of complex diagnostics technical infrastructure facilities and ensuring safe operation rolling stock in rail transport. In modern operating conditions of the railways of the Republic of Uzbekistan the canvas is subjected to intense train loads. In combination with the influence of many man-made, weather-climatic and geological factors, this leads to the occurrence of deformations in the subgrade, in including those that pose a threat to the safety of train traffic.

Methods: To stabilize subgrade sections where are happening deformation, are being developed and apply anti-deformation measures, the main basis for effective and rational design which is a detailed study engineering-geological conditions. However, such a survey sufficient completeness by traditional geological methods requires a significant amount of drilling, which is associated with large time and cost costs.

In addition, due to the inability to accommodate drilling equipment in the immediate vicinity of the railway track drilling is done with light machines or manually, which is not always provides the necessary depth of study of the section. Solving the issues of the completeness of the survey is related to the need to involve for the diagnosis of subgrade

and upper construction of the railway track modern methods of engineering shallow geophysics and video monitoring, which will provide conducting surveys in hard-to-reach conditions and allow obtaining continuous information as about the main elements of the geological structure, and the physical and mechanical properties of the medium.[1] So-called **Georadar method** allows to determine the thickness of structural subgrade layers, the quality of compaction of topside materials ways, as well as to identify areas of waterlogged and decompacted soils, voids and water infiltration zones. To solve the problem, an automated system has been developed georadar subgrade "GEOSKANER" and the system of visual detection of defects "RED", which are included in the list of systems high-speed diagnostic complex for automated evaluation the state of technical infrastructure facilities related to the provision traffic safety of **INTEGRAL trains**. The complex is capable simultaneously and synchronously measure more than 100 main parameters and track quality indicators, track facilities, contact network, railway automation and train radio communications, both at high (200 km/h.) and at a low working speed. The complex can work in difficult operational and climatic conditions, at low and high ambient .

1-fig.

Result. Integrated acquisition of all related parameters allows assess the actual state of technical infrastructure facilities related to with train traffic safety. All components of the complex are combined in a single high-speed onboard control and computer complex, receiving and processing results in real time measurements and video. Based on the obtained measurement results quality indicators of the infrastructure of all components are established components. The diagnostic complex is capable of performing the following functions:

- control of the geometrical parameters of the rail track;
- control of geometrical parameters of rails;
- determination of defects of the rails laid on the way;
- video monitoring of the presence (absence) of elements of the superstructure of the track;
- control of the dimensions of the approach of buildings;
- monitoring of the state of the ballast layer and the upper zone of the subgrade;
- assessment of the state of the contact network;
- diagnosing track devices of railway automation;

- checking the status of train radio communication during movement.

The complex will allow in the future to solve an urgent problem within the framework of increasing the speed and reliability of passenger and freight transportation of JSC "Uzbekistan temir yo'llari". Use of multiple control systems in within a single diagnostic train allows you to get significant advantages when conducting scheduled inspections of the condition of objects infrastructure:

- reduction of windows for checks by specialized mobile means and optimization of the train schedule;
- reduction of personnel costs of diagnostic tools;
- reduction in the number of allocated traction vehicles for driveways diagnostic tools;
- increasing the reliability of the analysis of the dynamics of the development of faults for integrated data monitoring account;
- simplification of the procedure for transferring the results of analysis for elimination malfunctions through the use of an automatic subsystem for issuing AS-TS assignments;
- maintenance of a single data archive of various subsystems;
- optimization of plans for the current maintenance and repair of facilities

infrastructure.

Developed by specialists of the company "Automated system georadar subgrade **"GEOSKANER"** is designed for monitoring the state of the ballast layer and the upper zone of the subgrade under the main site by GPR

when placing it on any specialized mobile unit. When moving (scan) georadar on the surface of the studied medium (railway embankment) on the monitor display the set signals (profile), by which you can determine the location, depth occurrence and extent of objects.

2-fig.

The system, when monitoring the subgrade, solves the following tasks:

- determination of the thickness and lithological structure of the ballast layer with the release of a layer of crushed stone contaminated with small particles and places with high humidity;
- determination of the position of the upper boundary of soils subgrade and its lithological structure under the main platform depth up to 4 m;
- allocation of places in the subgrade with weakened zones, characterized by low density and high humidity;
- presence of foreign bodies in the ballast layer and subgrade(cables, track structure elements, large stones, etc.);
- determination of the location of engineering structures; selection areas with laid coatings of geotextiles and expanded polystyrene;
- implementation of quality control of the completed overhaul way.[2]

The **GEOSCANNER** system provides recording, accumulation and storage data received during 8 hours of continuous work on each longitudinal profile and provides real-time viewing of records time. **SVOD visual defect detection system** designed to record a continuous video signal coming from 7 video cameras located under the car. The VOD system allows control:

- the presence of rail pads;
- condition of linings and fastenings;
- splashes of ballast;
- rail crossings, joints and insulating joints.

3-fig.

Incoming information from cameras located above the right and left rails used to visually detect defects on the surface skating. Incoming information from cameras located on the right and left side of the rail is used for visual identification:

- defects in fastenings, sleepers;
- splashing ballast;
- absence of bolted connections in rail joints.

Incoming information from a camera located between the tracks used for visual detection of sleeper defects and contamination ballast. All incoming information is accurately linked to the track coordinate and the ability to compare with data from other systems diagnostic path located in the diagnostic complex. [3]

Conclusions: The experience of using these systems in a single complex indicates that that GPR and video surveillance are gradually taking their rightful place in the arsenal of diagnostic tools for the infrastructure of railway facilities. Conducted a number of experimental runs of the diagnostic complex "INTEGRAL" in various engineering and geological conditions, which, clearly demonstrate the effectiveness of the application of geophysical methods in complex with other systems for monitoring and diagnostics problem sections of railways in order to establish the causes earth bed deformations.

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